

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF LEARNING THE RULES OF
COMPOSITION AND DEPICTION IN PAINTING

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Abstract. This article deals with the issues of composition in the works of famous artists, the requirements for composition and description in painting, the methods of composition, the materials used, and the methodology of creating different images for students in composition classes in higher education.

Keywords: Image, integrity, color, detail, contrast, idea, rhythm, artist, fragment.

The use of rules of composition in visual arts was formed from the time of the primitive community system. Primitive man expressed his concepts and ideas in the first ancient images.

When the people of the primitive period observe life with much intelligence, we see that they have a rather loosely developed sense of composition. This can be seen in the ancient images made by them in the rocks and caves. Images of various animals, scenes of hunting, herds are examples of creations of our ancient ancestors.

Our famous artists and heroes who made a great contribution to the development of the spiritual and cultural life of our country in the works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev entitled "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people" mentioning their names, he expressed the following thoughts: "The late masters of art such as Chingiz Ahmarov, Malik Nabiyeu, Urol Tansikboev, Rahim Ahmedov, Ravshan Mirtojiyev, people's artists of Uzbekistan, made a great contribution to the development of the portrait genre in Uzbek fine art. added. It is worth talking about the works of our famous artists Javlon Umarbekov, Bahadir Jalolov, Vladimir Burmakin, Ilhom Jabbarov, Akmal Ikromjonov, famous folk craftsman Artik Faizullayev.¹"

The basic laws of composition are objective in nature and apply to all types and genres of art. A student who knows the basic laws of composition can make a general-creative analysis of any artistic work. The following are the main laws of composition: the law of integrity, the law of contrasts, the law of typicality (creation of novelty), the law of subordinating all means of composition to the ideological content.

The Law of Integrity. This law is a view that unites all elements (unsur) and parts into a single whole, it is manifested everywhere in nature and society and appears as a dialectical law. According to this first law of composition - the law of integrity, the work of art is perceived as a whole, an indivisible whole.

The essence of this law can be revealed by analyzing its main features and characteristics. The main sign of the law of integrity is the indivisibility (unity) of the composition - it is understood that it is never perceived as several, even if it consists of small parts. Indivisibility finds its place in the composition through the constructive idea that can unite all the components of the future work into a whole.

Also, the law of integrity is manifested in the logical and emotional construction of the content, the psychological state of the characters in the image, the differences in the pose (stance) and movements of the figures, and the relationship. Among the works with a successful compositional

¹ Sh.Mirziyoyev.Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va olijanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz.T. O'zbekiston 2017.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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solution based on this law, I.E. Repin's "Unexpected", P.P. Ben'kov's "Friends", B. Jalolov's "The Birth of Dance", J. Umarbekov's "I am a Man" can be included.

Law of contrasts. There is a contradiction as an objective law in the life of nature and society. A sharp difference in the composition and quality of objects is understood as oppositional relations. In nature, color contrasts (red and green), tonal contrasts (lightness and darkness), shape contrasts (thin and thick), size contrasts (large and small) and others can be given as an example.

Until the 19th century, in portrait art, figures were depicted as light spots on a dark background. Caravaggio. "The lute player". In the 19th century, paintings with a dark silhouette on a light background appeared. For example, V.A. Serov's "Girl and Peach", "Stranger Woman" by I.N. Kramskoy, "Life Everywhere" by N.A. Yaroshenko are built on the contrast of the situation.

The law of typicality. One of the important laws related to the truthful depiction of life and the creation of an artistic image is typicality. By analyzing the appearances of existence, the artist reflects its essence, expresses its natural signs in the form of concrete artistic images. Typicality in the characters and the situation in which the event takes place is one of the signs of this law.

In the process of creating a work of art, the artist, knowing the laws of composition, develops, generalizes and typifies the driving personality of the work, as a result, the expressiveness and expressiveness of artistic images is brought to the highest level.

The following works correspond to the law of typicality: Leonardo da Vinci "Mona Lisa", Caravaggio "The Lutenist", I.E. Repin "The Priest", A. Abdullaev "Nazarali Niyazov", R. Choriev "The Bride", J. Umarbekov "Spiritual Painter" and others .

Typical images of representatives of different classes and classes were created in these works. These images are not concrete individuals in the work, but as a generalized collective image, they reveal the character of their age and time before the eyes of the viewer. Or the portraits of P.P. Benkov's "Hero's Mother" and N. Kashina's "Circle Girl" portray typical images. In the work "Portrait of Nazarali Niyazov" by artist A. Abdullaev, he created a generalized image of a typical Uzbek farmer with the image of an ordinary waterman. The law of subordinating all rules and means of composition to the ideological content. This law imposes on the artist the obligation to create a work that can be perceived as a whole, is expressive, and has a high ideological content. That is, it requires a composition built on the basis of the ideological content, and not on the basis of a dry scheme expressed in the form of all the details and parts of the work.

Rules of composition. The rules of composition consist of: rhythm, meaningful-compositional center, symmetry and asymmetry, showing the main thing in the background.

Rhythm. If symmetry provides a peaceful balance of elements, then rhythm implies movement, which does not stop, continues to infinity. Rhythm is the periodic repetition of a large or small event in life and art. It is the alternation of some similar element, symbolic situation, conditions, in a certain interval. Rhythm exists primarily in nature as a miraculous compositional beginning. expressed in contrasts (volume contrasts in sculpture).

By applying the law of contrasts, the rhythm becomes the components of the work and unites them.

Repetition of certain details or elements in the composition leads the viewer to observe and feel the content and its growth. This feature of the rhythm determines the interaction of the composition with the law of vitality, by which the artist is not limited to showing the external actions, but reveals the internal actions.

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Content-composition center. A certain part of the picture that sufficiently and clearly expresses the ideological content of the composition, the main one, is called a meaningful-compositional center. The compositional center is distinguished by its size, lighting and other means in accordance with the basic laws of composition. First of all, the compositional center must attract the attention of the audience.

The center of composition occupies a special place not only in painting, but also in sculpture, graphics, decorative arts and architecture.

The composition must be built taking into account the characteristics of human vision. The organization of the content-compositional center is connected with the same point of view, and only then, with a brighter expression, the main thing in the content of the artistic work becomes visible. For this reason, one of the main requirements of the composition is the correct placement of the meaningful-compositional center, which embodies the constructive idea of the content. It stands out from the public by being placed in the general background.

Symmetry. Symmetry in art in general, especially in fine art, takes its basis from real existence. Characteristic for the symmetrical organization of the composition is its balance in terms of volume components, color, color and even shapes. Asymmetry. Asymmetry is the opposite of symmetry in terms of structure. If the composition looks asymmetrical, then it is not symmetrical or vice versa. In an asymmetric composition, the balance is brought closer to each other by spatial breaks between the objects or completely separated. The balance is created by contrasting large and small, hunger and saturation contrast, bright and dull colors. Examples of such compositions are K.P. Bryullov's "The Last Day of Pompeii", A.A. Deineka's "Sports Girls" and many other works.

Parallelism in composition. It is known that the edges of the picture plane must end with the frame. The image is also connected with various parallel and non-parallel lines to match and not match the ideological content of the picture. The parallelism increases the effectiveness of other oblique or curved lines in the image.

In conclusion, we can say that worldview plays a very important role for an artist. The creative work created based on the rules of composition is perfect in every way and attracts the viewer. In order for the worldview to be high and full, the artist is not only informed by his knowledge, attitudes to life and society, his dreams, but also by his feeling of the world, which forms the true content of artistic creation.

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